

Chronic Kidney Disease

Sujith Kumar Palleti^{1,2*}, Sreekant Avula³, Roopa Naik^{4,5}

¹Department of Internal Medicine/Nephrology, Loyola University Medical Center, Maywood, USA

²Edward Hines Jr. Veterans Administration Hospital, Hines, USA

³Department of Internal Medicine/Endocrinology, University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, USA

⁴Department of Internal Medicine, Geisinger Commonwealth School of Medicine, Scranton, PA

⁵Geisinger Wyoming Valley Medical Center, Wilkes-Barre, PA

Citation: Sujith Kumar Palleti, Sreekant Avula, Roopa Naik. *Chronic Kidney Disease. Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(11):1-15.

Received Date: 05 May, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 09 May, 2023; **Published Date:** 10 May, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Sujith Kumar Palleti, Department of Internal Medicine/Nephrology, Loyola University Medical Center, Maywood, USA, Edward Hines Jr. Veterans Administration Hospital, Hines, USA

Copyright: © Sujith Kumar Palleti, Open Access 2023. This article, published in Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ) (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

The global increase in the number of patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) and the resulting end-stage renal failure requiring renal replacement therapy threatens to reach epidemic proportions in the next decade, and few countries have the strong economies to meet the challenges. As a result, a shift in the overall approach to CKD from end-stage renal disease (ESRD) treatment to considerably more active primary and secondary prevention is required. In this review, we examine the epidemiology of CKD worldwide, focusing on the early detection and prevention of CKD and the feasibility of CKD detection and primary prevention methods. We also look at risk factors and markers for progressive CKD. We examine the current understanding of the mechanisms leading to ESRD to inform current and future interventions and the evidence for interventions to slow the progression of CKD. Finally, we provide strategic recommendations based on future research to halt the global growth of chronic diseases.

Keywords: Kidney; Chronic Kidney Disease; Patients

INTRODUCTION

Epidemiology

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive disease characterized by structural and functional changes in the kidneys due to various etiologies. Chronic kidney disease is usually defined as a decline in kidney function, an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) of less than 60 mL/min/1.73 m², or evidence of kidney damage such as albuminuria, hematuria, or laboratory abnormalities or abnormal imaging and has been present for at least 3 months.

^[1] The global burden of CKD is significant and increasing, with approximately 10% of adults worldwide suffering from some form of CKD, resulting in 1.2 million deaths and 28.0 million life years lost annually.^[2] By 2040, CKD is estimated to be the fifth leading cause of death worldwide – one of the largest predicted causes of death.^[3]

The progressive nature of CKD and the resulting end-stage renal disease (ESRD) places a significant burden on global health resources.^[4] The global increase in the number of patients with chronic kidney disease is reflected in the increase in the number of people with end-stage renal disease receiving renal replacement therapy - dialysis or transplantation.^[5] The most important factors are the aging of the population; The incidence of ESRD is higher in older people than in the general population (in the United States, the annual incidence is greater than 1,200 per 1,200 million people over 65 years of age).^[6] Another factor is the global epidemic of type 2 diabetes; The number of people with diabetes in the world (currently around 154 million) is expected to double in the next 20 years. This increase is most important in less developed countries, where the number of people with diabetes may increase from 99 million to 286 million by 2025, accompanied by an epidemic of diabetic nephropathy.^[7] If the GFR is less than 15 ml/min per 1.73 m², a person has reached end-stage renal disease (ESKD), when kidney function can no longer sustain life in the long term. Options for patients with ESKD include renal replacement therapy (in the form of dialysis or a kidney transplant) or conservative therapy (also called palliative or nondialysis therapy).

Causes of chronic kidney disease:

In developed countries, CKD is often associated with old age, diabetes, hypertension, obesity, and cardiovascular disease, and diabetic glomerulosclerosis and hypertensive nephrosclerosis are putative pathological entities; however, accurate diagnosis is often difficult.^[8] Diabetic glomerulosclerosis is characterized by slowly worsening albuminuria, hypertension, and a progressive decline in GFR, sometimes with nephrotic syndrome. Hypertensive nephrosclerosis has no clear signs of kidney damage, but albuminuria can occur from high to high normal levels after a decline in GFR. Many diabetics and CKD patients do not have the typical features of diabetic glomerulosclerosis, and the pathological findings of hypertensive nephrosclerosis are often more severe than expected from blood pressure levels.^[9,10] The presence of red or white blood cells or certain imaging abnormalities indicates another kidney disease. In developing countries, glomerular and tubulointerstitial diseases caused by infections and exposure to drugs and toxins are also common causes of CKD.

Prevalence of chronic kidney disease:

Many countries have surveillance programs for renal failure treated with dialysis and transplantation.^[11] Incidence and prevalence vary due to differences in the prevalence of underlying diseases and the availability of government-sponsored therapy. Today, the incidence is up to 200 cases per million years in many countries. That is almost 400 cases per million in the United States^[12] and some places in Mexico. Dialysis is the main treatment of choice for most patients and situations. The median survival in the United States is 3 to 5 years, and the incidence is nearly 1,800 cases per million. In Japan and Taiwan, the high survival rate implies a high prevalence of almost 2400 cases per million.^[13] Diabetes is the leading cause of kidney failure in most countries, accounting for at least 40% of new patients. Racial and ethnic minorities in the United States have high disease rates, likely reflecting genetic and environmental factors in susceptibility differences in treatment.^[12]

CKD staging:

CKD stages as defined by the National Kidney Foundation of the United States and the Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative^[14]

Stage 1

Kidney damage (pathological abnormalities or evidence of damage, such as abnormalities in blood or urine tests or imaging studies) with normal or increased glomerular filtration rate (90 mL per minute per 1.73 m²)

Stage 2

Glomerular filtration rate of 60-89 mL per minute per 1.73 m² with signs of kidney damage

Stage 3

Glomerular filtration rate is 30-59 mL per minute per 1.73 m².

Stage 4

Glomerular filtration rate is 15-29 mL per minute per 1.73 m².

Stage 5 or End-stage renal failure

Glomerular filtration rate of <15 mL per minute per 1.73 m².

When to consult a nephrologist:

Referrals of patients with chronic renal failure to nephrologists vary according to the specifics of regional healthcare systems and are often not standardized even within countries. However, the following features usually indicate the need for nephrology follow-up.^[15]

1. GFR < 30ml/min/1.73m².
2. A reduction in GFR of at least 25%.
3. Progression of CKD with sustained decrease in GRF >5 mL/min per year.
4. A consistent finding of significant proteinuria.
5. Persistently unexplained hematuria.
6. Secondary hyperparathyroidism, persistent metabolic acidosis, anemia due to erythropoietin deficiency.
7. Hypertension was resistant to treatment with 4 or more antihypertensive drugs.
8. Persistent abnormalities in serum potassium.
9. Recurrent or extensive kidney stones.
10. Unknown cause of hereditary kidney disease or CKD.

Risk factors for chronic kidney disease:

Susceptibility factors

CKD tends to run in families, suggesting a genetic or familial predisposition.^[16] Genetic studies have shown associations between CKD and various changes or polymorphisms in candidate genes encoding putative neurotransmitters, including the renin-angiotensin system. Racial factors such as a high prevalence of chronic

diseases associated with hypertension, diabetes, or both among Africans and Native Americans in the United States and Afro-Caribbeans and Asians in the United Kingdom also contribute to susceptibility to CKD.^[17] Low birth weight and childhood malnutrition in some ethnic minorities may be associated with a reduced quantity of nephrons, which predisposes to hypertension and kidney disease later in life. Men and the elderly may also be more susceptible to chronic disease, which explains the high proportion of these populations in renal replacement therapy programs.

Initiating factors

Many cohort studies have previously identified hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidemia, obesity, and smoking as risk factors or markers for the development of CKD in the general population.^[18] Common risk factors and markers appear to be associated with both renal and cardiovascular disease in developed countries. Also, albuminuria itself predicts not only chronic disease but also cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Kidney failure is also a major risk factor for those with cardiovascular disease.^[19] Thus, early detection and prevention can influence both renal and cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. The risk factors listed above, especially diabetes and hypertension, are also likely to affect people in less developed countries with a "Western" lifestyle. Diabetic nephropathy is now one of the main causes of ESRD in most countries (more than 30-40%). Developing countries continue to suffer from infectious diseases, including infection-related glomerulonephritis and resulting renal failure. Infections include HIV (40 million infections worldwide), hepatitis C virus (170 million), malaria (300 million cases per year), schistosomiasis (200 million), and tuberculosis (200 million).^[20-22] The increase in CKD cases due to these infections is likely to match the increase in the number of infected individuals.

Progressive factors

The progression of CKD is variable and depends on several risk factors or markers. Immutable factors include genetics, race, age, and gender. For example, there is considerable evidence that chronic disease progresses more rapidly in the elderly, men, or African Americans.^[23,24]

Hypertension and proteinuria:

The most important modifiable progression factor is systemic hypertension. Proteinuria is a reliable marker of the severity of CKD and a strong and independent predictor of its progression.^[25] There is controversy as to whether proteinuria is a risk factor for the progression of clinical nephropathies. Patients with persistently high urinary protein excretion (> 3-5 g/24 h) usually have much more rapid progression than patients with mild to moderate proteinuria (15 pack years). In another study, heavy smokers (> 20 pack-years) had three times the risk of albuminuria compared to nonsmokers.

Anti-inflammatory drugs:

Some studies have linked the use of pain relievers, particularly paracetamol, and NSAIDs, to an increased risk of CKD.^[30,31] One of the largest case-control studies (716 patients with end-stage disease) found that patients who took at least 5,000 paracetamol tablets in their lifetime had a 2.4 odds compared to those who took 1,000 or less. In the

same study, NSAID use was associated with an odds ratio of 8.8, while aspirin use did not appear to be associated with an increased risk of ESRD. Many such studies have been criticized for serious errors, including confounding due to indications.

Measures to preserve kidney function:

Primary prevention

Lifestyle measures

Primary prevention is based on controlling the global obesity epidemic and the associated type 2 diabetes and hypertension. Lifestyle changes such as weight loss, exercise, and dietary manipulation can be effective, as these tools have significantly reduced the incidence of type 2 diabetes in overweight people with impaired glucose tolerance.^[32] Limiting dietary salt and eating lots of fruits and vegetables and diets low in saturated fat are recommended to control blood pressure. Improved public health education, weight reduction, regular exercise, and diet should lead to long-term reductions in the number of people with diabetes and hypertension, as they account for the largest number of future cases of chronic COPD. Whether such lifestyle approaches are sustainable in the long term remains to be seen. The success of lifestyle changes to prevent obesity, diabetes, and hypertension depends largely on the commitment of policymakers and governments to implement them. The WHO Integrated Program for the Prevention of Noncommunicable Diseases focuses on common risk factors for chronic disease and is increasingly aware of the links between hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and chronic disease.^[33-35]

Plant-based diet

In many causes of CKD, afferent arterioles are relatively dilated, and efferent arterioles are relatively narrowed as a compensatory mechanism to maintain glomerular filtration rate in the short term, a process called glomerular hyperfiltration or intraglomerular hypertension. This interaction is regulated in part by tubuloglomerular feedback.^[36] In the long term, glomerular hyperfiltration can cause further damage to the kidney through mechanical stress and activation of inflammatory mediators that promote interstitial fibrosis. Dietary protein restriction, by increasing afferent arterial tone, can alleviate intraglomerular hypertension, moderate renal interstitial fibrosis, and slow the progression of CKD.^[37] This effect parallels and complements the postglomerular effect of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone pathway modulators, such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors and angiotensin receptor blockers, which reduce glomerular pressure by promoting efferent arterial vasodilation.

Physical activity, obesity, and weight loss

Obesity is a hallmark of the metabolic syndrome and is associated with chronic kidney disease. Evidence suggests that increases in adiposity (eg, body mass index and waist circumference) are independently associated with decreases in glomerular filtration rate.^[38] This association may be due to systemic and intraglomerular blood pressure, the effect of prediabetic blood glucose levels on podocyte stress, and other unknown factors. Physical activity is a key component of weight loss lifestyle modification strategies to have a positive effect on the progression of CKD. Various weight loss measures may be recommended for people with CKD. Calorie restriction

combined with a plant-based, low-protein diet can lead to gradual weight loss in most people with obesity and CKD. The role of bariatric surgery in reducing the risk of CKD is also uncertain.^[39] Gastric bypass surgery increases the remission of albuminuria in individuals with type 2 diabetes, obesity, and microalbuminuria compared with optimal medical therapy and may be an important treatment option for selected individuals.

Secondary prevention of progression

There is a wide range of interventions that can slow progression in patients with established CKD. Blood pressure control is the most effective intervention.^[40] In patients with chronic kidney disease, the target blood pressure should be less than 130/80 mmHg without diabetes or significant proteinuria (1g per 24 hours) and less than 125/75 mmHg in patients with diabetes and proteinuria. more than 1 g in 24 hours. These recommendations and guidelines are based on the results of several clinical trials in diabetic and non-diabetic nephropathy.^[41]

Blockade of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, mineralocorticoid receptor antagonism, and other antihypertensive drugs

Control of proteinuria and inhibition of the renin-angiotensin system are important factors in slowing the progression of diabetic and non-diabetic CKD.^[41] Antihypertensive approaches with angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors or angiotensin-2 receptor blockers have been widely recommended. The effect of inhibition of the renin-angiotensin system on the progression of CKD appears to be proportional to the antihypertensive and antiproteinuric effects. According to recent findings from the African-American Kidney Disease and Hypertension Study, the effectiveness of ACE inhibitors in African-Americans is similar to that in white patients.

Strict glycemic and lipid control:

Tight control of diabetes slows the progression of diabetic nephropathy.^[42] Based on data from studies such as the Diabetes Control and Complications Study and the UK Future Diabetes Study, a glycosylated hemoglobin target of around 7% is recommended. Lipid-lowering with hydroxymethylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase inhibitors (statins) is protective in experimental models of chronic kidney disease. These drugs can have a synergistic effect on the renal protection provided by ACE inhibitors and angiotensin-2 receptors.^[43] Studies have shown that lowering lipids in patients with CKD may be protective. Statins can reduce cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in addition to lowering serum cholesterol levels, justifying their use in CKD patients at high CVD risk.

Multi-drug therapy:

The concept of multidrug therapy was introduced after a meta-analysis of more than 750 studies involving approximately 400 000 participants suggested that CVD events could be reduced by up to 80% with the combination of ACE inhibitors, statins, and others. cardioprotective agents such as aspirin and antioxidants.^[44] It remains to be seen whether a similar therapeutic approach based on a combination of generic drugs would be appropriate in the future for some patients with progressive CKD.

Cardiovascular disease and the progression of chronic kidney disease:

Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death in patients with CKD and therefore focuses on conservative management of this population.^[45] Low eGFR and higher albuminuria are independently associated with a higher risk of cardiovascular events (in addition to traditional risk factors such as blood pressure, high cholesterol, and lifestyle. Although traditional common risks factors such as overweight, hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidemia, and smoking). are associated with cardiovascular disease in patients who already have chronic kidney disease, many nontraditional risk factors increase the risk of cardiovascular disease, especially in patients with advanced CKD.^[46, 47] These so-called kidney-specific factors include inflammation with or without. protein-energy wasting, mineral and bone disturbances, and endothelial dysfunction.

Acute kidney injury

Patients with chronic kidney disease, especially advanced kidney disease (eGFR less than 30 mL/min/1.73 m²), often do not show a linear progression of the disease, which may be related to overlapping episodes of acute kidney injury or other factors.^[48] Some (but not all) studies show that any acute kidney injury can accelerate the progression of CKD. Therefore, prevention of acute kidney injury is an important part of CKD management.^[49] This precaution includes avoiding drug combinations associated with acute kidney injury (eg, ACE inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers in combination with loop diuretics and NSAIDs) 1 and avoiding infections that may cause hypotension or septic shock requiring potentially nephrotoxic agents. antimicrobial agents.^[50] Other predisposing factors for acute kidney injury include cardiovascular events, especially heart failure, which causes venous congestion and decreased renal perfusion, coronary artery bypass grafting, and other major surgeries, which are associated with possible intraoperative hypotensive episodes.^[51]

Complications:

Uremic complications

Many diseases associated with uremia are usually asymptomatic and are first recognized below approximately 60 mL/min with a GFR of 1.73 m².^[52] These disorders occur more often when GFR decreases, and with a GFR of 15-30 mL/min/1.73 m², the incidence of hypertension is approximately 75%; 50% for anemia; 20% in hyperparathyroidism, hyperphosphatemia, and acidosis; and 5-10% in hypocalcemia and low serum albumin.^[53]

Impairment of excretory and endocrine functions of the kidneys, accompanied by a decrease in GFR, leads to complex disorders characterized by solute retention, hormonal deficiency or resistance, and compensatory reactions in other organ systems. For any disorder, these abnormalities serve as indicators of disease severity and targets for intervention. Clinical trials have shown that several interventions are successful in improving marker abnormalities, but evidence of long-term efficacy in clinical outcome measures for many therapies is limited.

Salt retention and hypertension:

Hypertension is caused by salt accumulation and increased vascular tone due to suppression of the sympathetic nervous system and the renin-angiotensin system, inhibition of sodium-potassium ATPase, and lack of nitric oxide.^[54] Although sodium restriction reduces blood pressure in experimental models, compliance in clinical practice is low. All antihypertensive medications appear to be effective in lowering blood pressure, but multiple agents, including a diuretic, are usually required to achieve target blood pressure. The optimal level of blood pressure and the choice of antihypertensive drugs to reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease are controversial. Guidelines suggest that lower-than-normal blood pressure targets (110 g/L or 120 g/L) are consistently associated with high rates of cardiovascular disease, particularly in patients who respond poorly to ESAs.^[56-58] Clinical decision-making must balance risks and benefits and generally favors ESA administration in dialysis patients with lower hemoglobin levels, poorer quality of life, and more frequent transfusion requirements than in patients with preexisting CKD.

Bone and Mineral Disorders:

Mineral and bone diseases in chronic kidney disease are characterized by abnormalities in the concentration of serum calcium, phosphorus, 1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol, and parathyroid hormone; abnormalities of bone morphology; and vascular calcification.^[59-61] Phosphate retention and 1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol deficiency appear to be the main causes of hyperparathyroidism and hypocalcemia and can be treated by reducing phosphorus intake (dietary protein restriction) and using phosphate-binding drugs (calcium carbonate, lanthanum carbonate, and sevelcarboxonate). Hyperparathyroidism can also be treated with exogenous 1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol and vitamin D analogs and calcium. Although these measures can reduce the severity of osteitis fibrosa cystica, they do not reduce the incidence of fractures. 1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol and calcium-containing phosphate binders have a greater risk of hypercalcemia than non-calcium phosphate binders and may cause small circulation osteomalacia and vascular calcification. However, the long-term consequences of these effects are unknown. Fibroblast growth factor (FGF)-23 - a bone-derived phosphate hormone - is secreted in response to phosphorus intake, inhibits 1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol production, and is associated with cardiovascular disease. Increased FGF-23 in CKD may represent an alternative mechanism in mineral and bone diseases and a new target for interventions.

Peripheral artery disease:

The incidence of peripheral artery disease (PAD) is higher in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) than in the general population.^[62,63] PAD is a strong independent risk factor for cardiovascular mortality and morbidity, including limb amputation, in people with CKD. Aggressive risk factor modification, including treatment of diabetes, hyperlipidemia, hypertension, and smoking cessation, as well as preventive foot care interventions and a multidisciplinary approach involving podiatrists and vascular and wound care specialists, should be used to reduce amputations. Revascularization in critical limb ischemia is associated with poor outcomes in patients with CKD and PAD. Future studies are recommended to evaluate the utility of earlier treatment strategies in this high CVD-risk population with CKD.

Malnutrition and inflammation:

Malnutrition and inflammation are common in CKD.^[64] Reduced energy intake is an important causal factor, but dietary interventions are usually not sufficient to increase intake. The inflammation may be due in part to systemic vascular disease and accumulated solute. Clinical trials are underway with exercise and anabolic agents such as human growth hormone and ghrelin. Peripheral and central nervous system disorders include peripheral neuropathy, restless legs syndrome, sleep disturbances, and cognitive impairment. Accumulated toxins are thought to play a role in these disorders, and intensive dialysis is sometimes associated with improvement. Specific treatments for these neurological symptoms have not yet been developed.

Dialysis and organ transplantation

The high cost of dialysis and transplantation limits their availability worldwide, and many patients with kidney failure die without treatment. In 2008, Medicare payments in the United States ranged from \$77 to \$506 per year for hemodialysis, \$57 to \$639 for peritoneal dialysis, and \$26 to \$668 for transplantation.^[65,66] Observational studies show that referral to a nephrologist before the onset of renal failure is associated with increased transplant rates and mortality and costs after initiation of dialysis; however, the results of a clinical trial did not show an advantage of early initiation of dialysis.^[67] The early referral also allows patients to make informed decisions about modalities, establish vascular access for hemodialysis, and identify living donors for transplantation before renal failure occurs. The one-year survival rate with a functioning graft after a deceased donor transplant is now over 90%. However, after 10 years, this proportion is less than 40%, partly due to the nephrotoxic effects of calcineurin inhibitors and death due to graft dysfunction due to cardiovascular disease.^[68] Clinical trials focus on low doses of these agents in combination with other immunosuppressive agents to reduce the risk of nephrotoxicity and cardiovascular disease and prevent graft rejection. Observational studies indicate that reduced GFR and albuminuria are risk factors for graft loss and mortality in kidney transplant recipients. Guidelines for nonspecific therapy to slow the progression of kidney disease and prevent the complications of reduced GFR and albuminuria are largely based on observational data and extrapolation from studies of primary kidney disease. Organ transplantation is largely limited by the shortage of organs. Although initial experiences with donor exchange programs or recipient desensitization show promising results in overcoming ABO and HLA incompatibility, logistical obstacles must be overcome before these operations can be used worldwide.

Long-term dialysis patients have significantly lower survival rates than transplant recipients, even after accounting for selection and case mix. Survival results for hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis are similar.^[69] Peritonitis is a common complication of peritoneal dialysis, leading to catheter loss in some cases.^[70] Age-adjusted survival of dialysis patients has improved over the past decade with new technologies and clinical performance measures, including increasing dialysis doses, partial correction of anemia, and control of hyperphosphatemia. However, clinical trials of individual interventions have not shown improvement in survival. One study showed improvements in left ventricular mass and physical function with repeated hemodialysis, possibly indicating improved fluid and blood pressure control. Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death, but the association of traditional risk factors such as blood pressure, serum LDL cholesterol, and body mass index with mortality is complex, with risk increasing at both low and high levels.

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER ACTIONS

Chronic kidney disease is one of many chronic diseases that mostly affects the elderly and significantly increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. Coordinating public health interventions for CKD and other chronic diseases is likely to be the most effective strategy. Reorganization of care services is likely to be necessary to effectively care for the elderly and other people with various chronic conditions, as well as collaboration at all levels with government and private organizations. Evaluating the effectiveness of public health strategies is important to guide progress. The main goal of conservative treatment of CKD is to slow the progression of CKD to prolong dialysis-free time, achieving the best quality of life and survival through kidney-sparing treatment. These strategies also include effective treatment of renal and non-renal diseases and associated symptoms. Research programs for detection and prevention are essential. Early detection and subsequent treatment of CKD met many, but not all, of the criteria for an ideal screening program.^[71] Primary prevention can be warranted after identifying individuals at risk of developing CKD with the earliest signs of kidney damage. Carefully conducted and well-designed studies are needed to determine the true incidence and prevalence of all stages of CKD in different populations, the sensitivity of screening methods in the early stages of CKD, the natural history of stages 1 and 2 of CKD, and the cost-effectiveness of primary and early secondary interventions. There are similarities and differences between kidney-sparing treatment and supportive care for CKD.

Nutritional interventions such as a low-salt and plant-dominant, low-protein diet and pharmacotherapeutics such as renin-angiotensin-aldosterone pathway modulators, SGLT2 inhibitors, and the newer nonsteroidal mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists should be used as widely as possible. Preference should be given to adequately powered randomized trials to evaluate the effect of new pharmacotherapies in slowing the progression of CKD and preventing its complications, especially in the early stages of the disease. If dialysis is necessary and a kidney transplant cannot be provided, a gradual and gradual transition to dialysis can preserve kidney function longer. Some patients may benefit from palliative ultrafiltration dialysis to relieve fluid overload and associated symptoms.^[72] Future research on strategies to replace or supplement dialysis should include, among others, intestinal dialysis, diaphoresis for uremia, and fluid and electrolyte regulation, based on the results of studies in relevant animal models.^[73] Future studies are needed to refine current interventions and explore new models and strategies to prolong renal and patient survival, if possible without dialysis, and help patients live longer and well with CKD.

REFERENCES

1. Wesson D, Mathur V, Tangri N, Stasiv Y, Parsell D, Li E, et al. Veverimer versus placebo in patients with metabolic acidosis associated with chronic kidney disease: a multicentre, randomised, double-blind, controlled, phase 3 trial. Lancet. 2019;393(10179):1417-1427.
2. Jeffrey A Kraut, Ira Kurtz. Metabolic acidosis of CKD: diagnosis, clinical characteristics, and treatment. Am J Kidney Dis. 2005;45(6):978-93.

3. Yi-Chun Tsai, Jer-Chia Tsai, Szu-Chia Chen, Yi-Wen Chiu, Shang-Jyh Hwang, Chi-Chih Hung, et al. Association of fluid overload with kidney disease progression in advanced CKD: a prospective cohort study. Am J Kidney Dis. 2014;63(1):68-75.
4. Lysaght Michael J. Maintenance dialysis population dynamics: current trends and long-term implications. J Am Soc Nephrol . 2002;13 Suppl 1:S37-40.
5. Palleti, Sujith Kumar, Sreekanth Avula, Sandesh Dewan. Kidney: A Review on End Stage Renal Disease, Dialysis and Transplant. Int Clinc Med Case Rep Jour. 2023;2(10):1-8.
6. Eggers Paul W. Has the incidence of end-stage renal disease in the USA and other countries stabilized? Curr Opin Nephrol Hypertens. 2011;20(3):241-5.
7. King H, Aubert RE, Herman WH. Global burden of diabetes, 1995-2025: prevalence, numerical estimates, and projections. Diabetes Care. 1998;21(9):1414-31.
8. Joseph Lunyera, Dinushika Mohottige, Megan Von Isenburg, Marc Jeuland, Uptal D Patel, John W Stanifer. CKD of uncertain etiology: a systematic review. Clin J Am Soc Nephrol. 2016;11(3):379-85.
9. Hans-Joachim Anders, Tobias B Huber, Berend Isermann, Mario Schiffer. CKD in diabetes: diabetic kidney disease versus nondiabetic kidney disease. Nat Rev Nephrol. 2018;14(6):361-377.
10. Raza A Khan, Nidhi Patel, Atunde Folajimi, Bansari Raveena Bai, Vrushak Patel, Praveen Kumar Kommenni, et al. Comparison of the Efficacy and Safety of Metformin-Based Combination Therapy Versus Metformin Alone in Children and Adolescents With Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Meta-Analysis. Cureus. 2023;15(2):e35014.
11. Josef Coresh, Tazeen H Jafar. Disparities in worldwide treatment of kidney failure. Lancet. 2015;385(9981):1926-1928.
12. Josef Coresh 1, Elizabeth Selvin, Lesley A Stevens, Jane Manzi, John W Kusek, Paul Eggers, et al. Prevalence of chronic kidney disease in the United States. JAMA. 2007;298(17): 2038-2047.
13. Kunihiro Yamagata, Takashi Yagisawa, Shigeru Nakai, Masaaki Nakayama, Enyu Imai, Motoshi Hattori, et al. Prevalence and incidence of chronic kidney disease stage G5 in Japan. Clin Exp Nephrol. 2015;19(1):54-64.
14. Andrew S Levey, Josef Coresh, Ethan Balk, Annamaria T Kausz, Adeera Levin, Michael W Steffes, et al. National Kidney Foundation practice guidelines for chronic kidney disease: evaluation, classification, and stratification. Ann Intern Med. 2003;139(2):137-47.
15. Virginia A Moyer. Screening for chronic kidney disease: US Preventive Services Task Force recommendation statement. Ann Intern Med. 2003;139(2):137-47.
16. Bridget M Lin, Girish N Nadkarni, Ran Tao, Mariaelisa Graff, Myriam Fornage, Steven Buyske, et al. Genetics of chronic kidney disease stages across ancestries: The PAGE study. Front Genet. 2019;10:494.
17. Michael F Flessner, Sharon B Wyatt, Ermeg L Akylbekova, Sean Coady, Tibor Fulop, Frederick Lee, et al. Prevalence and awareness of CKD among African Americans: The Jackson heart study. Am J Kidney Dis. 2009;53(2):238-47.
18. Eknayan G. Obesity and chronic kidney disease. Nefrología (English Edition). 2011;31(4):397-403.

19. Sameer Muhammad Ali, et al. Comparison of Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting Combined With Mitral Valve Repair Versus Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting Alone in Patients With Moderate Ischemic Mitral Regurgitation: A Meta-Analysis. Cureus. 2023;15:4.
20. Noble Rebecca, Maarten W Taal. Epidemiology and causes of chronic kidney disease. *Medicine*. 2019;47(9):562-566.
21. Fareeha Naseer Syed, Nadia Kashif, Mubashir Razzaq Khan, Fayaz Ahmed Memon, Muhammad Zubair Jabbar, Sujith Kumar Palleti, et al. Hepatitis C Virus Infection in Patients with Beta Thalassemia after Multiple Transfusions at a Tertiary Care Hospital. Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences. 2023;17(01):363-363.
22. Palleti Sujith K, et al. Study about Sphingobium Lactosutens: A Human Pathogen Causing Peritoneal Dialysis Related Peritonitis." *Perspective of Recent Advances in Medical Research*. BP International 9. 2023:31-35.
23. Mary Hannan, Sajid Ansari, Natalie Meza, Amanda H Anderson, Anand Srivastava, Sushrut Waikar, et al. Risk factors for CKD progression: overview of findings from the CRIC study. Clin J Am Soc Nephrol. 2021;16(4):648-659.
24. Abdulmaleek Idanesimhe Sado, Muhammad S Afzal, Lavanya Kannekant, Hrushikesh Reddy Pamreddy, Jorge Pimentel Campillo, Vaishnavi Kandukuri, et al. A Meta-Analysis on Predictors of Mortality Among Patients Hospitalized for Acute Exacerbation of Asthma. Cureus. 2023;15(2):e35225.
25. Stephanie Lankhorst, Mariëtte H W Kappers, Joep H M van Esch, A H Jan Danser, Anton H van den Meiracker. Mechanism of hypertension and proteinuria during angiogenesis inhibition: evolving role of endothelin-1. J Hypertens. 2013;31(3):444-54; discussion 454.
26. Digsu N Koye, Dianna J Magliano, Christopher M Reid, Christopher Jepsen, Harold I Feldman, William H Herman, et al. Risk of progression of nonalbuminuric CKD to end-stage kidney disease in people with diabetes: the CRIC (Chronic Renal Insufficiency Cohort) Study. Am J Kidney Dis . 2018;72(5):653-661.
27. Rakesh Pilla, Sujith Kumar Palleti, Renuka Rayana, Satish Reddy Skss, Aminah Abdul Razzack, Sruti Kalla. Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) variations in nondiabetics with nutritional anemia. Cureus . 2020;12(11):e11479.
28. Nehus Edward. Obesity and chronic kidney disease. *Curr Opin Pediatr* . 2018;30(2):241-246.
29. Jia Xia, Lin Wang, Zhiheng Ma, Liping Zhong, Ying Wang, Yachan Gao, et al. Cigarette smoking and chronic kidney disease in the general population: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies. Nephrol Dial Transplant . 2017;32(3):475-487.
30. Katherine Gooch, Bruce F Culleton, Braden J Manns, Jianguo Zhang, Helman Alfonso, Marcello Tonelli, et al. NSAID use and progression of chronic kidney disease. Am J Med . 2007;120(3):280.e1-7.
31. Sujith K Palleti, Anuradha Wadhwa, Abdul H Rasheed. The First Case of Ceftazidime-Induced Antibiomania: A Case Report and Literature Review. Cureus. 2022;14(12):e32904.
32. Shalini Verma, M Ejaz Hussain. Obesity and diabetes: an update. Diabetes Metab Syndr. 2017;11(1):73-79.

33. John R Petrie, Tomasz J Guzik, Rhian M Touyz. Diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease: clinical insights and vascular mechanisms. Can J Cardiol . 2018;34(5):575-584.
34. Jithin Karedath, Fnu Avanteeka, Muhammad Nouman Aslam, Ahmad Nadeem, Rao Ahmed Yousaf, Sandesh Shah, et al. Comparison of Effectiveness and Safety of Low-Dose Versus Standard-Dose Intravenous Recombinant Tissue Plasminogen Activator in Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Meta-Analysis. Cureus. 2023;15(2):e35571.
35. Palleti Sujith K, Anuradha Wadhwa, Abdul H. Rasheed. Ceftazidime-induced Antibiotomania: A Rare Case Study and Review of Literature." Research Highlights in Disease and Health Research. 2023;56-61.
36. Vallon Volker. Tubuloglomerular feedback and the control of glomerular filtration rate. News Physiol Sci. 2003;18:169-74.
37. Hyunju Kim, Laura E Caulfield, Vanessa Garcia-Larsen, Lyn M Steffen, Morgan E Grams, Josef Coresh, et al. Plant-based diets and incident CKD and kidney function. Clin J Am Soc Nephrol . 2019;14(5):682-691.
38. Chang Alex R, et al. Adiposity and risk of decline in glomerular filtration rate: meta-analysis of individual participant data in a global consortium. Bmj. 2019:364.
39. Allon N Friedman, Abdus S Wahed, Junyao Wang, Anita P Courcoulas, Gregory Dakin, Marcelo W Hinojosa, et al. Effect of bariatric surgery on CKD risk J Am Soc Nephrol. 2018;29(4):1289-1300.
40. Elaine Ku, Benjamin J. Lee, Jenny Wei , Matthew R. Weir. Hypertension in CKD: core curriculum 2019. American Journal of Kidney Diseases. 2019;74(1):120-131.
41. UK Prospective Diabetes Study Group. Tight blood pressure control and risk of macrovascular and microvascular complications in type 2 diabetes: UKPDS 38. BMJ. 1998;317(7160):703-13.
42. P Hovind , P Rossing, L Tarnow, U M Smidt, H H Parving. Progression of diabetic nephropathy. Kidney Int. 2001;59(2):702-9.
43. Xiaole Su, Lu Zhang, Jicheng Lv, Jinwei Wang, Wanyin Hou, Xinfang Xie, et al. Effect of statins on kidney disease outcomes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Am J Kidney Dis. 2016;67(6):881-92.
44. A Meguid El Nahas , Aminu K Bello. Chronic kidney disease: the global challenge. Lancet. 2005;365(9456):331-40.
45. Charles A Herzog 1, Richard W Asinger, Alan K Berger, David M Charytan, Javier Díez, Robert G Hart, et al. Cardiovascular disease in chronic kidney disease. A clinical update from Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO). Kidney Int. 2011;80(6):572-86.
46. Joachim Jankowski, Jürgen Floege, Danilo Fliser, Michael Böhm, Nikolaus Marx. Cardiovascular disease in chronic kidney disease: pathophysiological insights and therapeutic options. 2021;143(11):1157-1172.
47. Kashyap Kela, Chaitanya Rojulpote, Ajinkya Buradkar, Sreekant Avula, Vijay Pratap Singh, Sujithraj Dommaraju, et al. An unusual cause of abnormal echodensity in the right atrium. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2021;77(18_Supplement_1):2698.
48. Lakhmir S Chawla 1, Richard L Amdur, Susan Amodeo, Paul L Kimmel, Carlos E Palant. The severity of acute kidney injury predicts progression to chronic kidney disease. Kidney Int. 2011;79(12):1361-9.

49. Sai Kiran Kondabolu, Yasitha Kakarlapudi, Haider Malik, Hamza Malik, Saima Khan, Praveen Kumar Komminni, et al. Beneficial Impacts of Fenoldopam on Patients With or at Risk for Acute Renal Failure and Undergoing Surgery: A Meta-Analysis of Randomized Clinical Trials. Cureus. 2023;15(2):e34584.
50. Abshiro H Mayo, Fatima Ahmad, Muhammad Sohaib Afzal, Muhammad Usama Khokhar, Daneyal Rafique, Sai Krishna Vallamchetla, et al. A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Independent Predictors for Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome in Patients Presenting With Sepsis. Cureus. 2023;15(4):e37055.
51. Karthik Gonuguntla , Komal Ejaz , Chaitanya Rojulpote , Ayesha Shaik , Abhijit Bhattaru , Tapan Buch, et al. A nationwide cohort analysis to determine the prevalence of sinus node dysfunction and rates of pacemaker implantation in systemic lupus erythematosus. Am J Cardiovasc Dis. 2021;11(4):478-483.
52. Flore Duranton, Gerald Cohen, Rita De Smet, Mariano Rodriguez, Joachim Jankowski, Raymond Vanholder, et al. Normal and pathologic concentrations of uremic toxins. J Am Soc Nephrol. 2012;23(7):1258-70.
53. Saksham, Sharma, et al. Developments in application of optogenetics in pain and anxiety: a literature review. Scientific Collection Inter Conf. 2023;31(147):209-225.
54. M Weinstock , E Gorodetsky, R Kalman. Renal denervation prevents sodium retention and hypertension in salt-sensitive rabbits with genetic baroreflex impairment. Clin Sci (Lond). 1996;90(4):287-93.
55. Melissa E. Stauffer, Tao Fan. Prevalence of anemia in chronic kidney disease in the United States. PLoS One. 2014; 9(1): e84943.
56. Julia Bohlius, Simon Langensiepen, Guido Schwarzer, Jerome Seidenfeld, Margaret Piper, Charles Bennett, Andreas Engert. Recombinant human erythropoietin and overall survival in cancer patients: results of a comprehensive meta-analysis. J Natl Cancer Inst . 2005;97(7):489-98.
57. Robin Rauniyar, Rahul Rauniyar, Ankita Agrawal, Shikha Yadav, Sreekant Avula. Severe late-onset neutropenia induced by ocrelizumab in a multiple sclerosis patient: A case report. Clin Case Rep. 2022;10(1):e05299.
58. Aiman Wajeeda, et al. MM-082 Addition of Daratumumab to Drug Regimens in the Treatment of Multiple Myeloma: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Clinical Trials. Clinical Lymphoma Myeloma and Leukemia. 2022;22: S405.
59. Kevin J Martin, Esther A González. Metabolic bone disease in chronic kidney disease. J Am Soc Nephrol. 2007;18(3):875-85.
60. Benaicha K, Khenhrani R, Veer M. Efficacy of Molnupiravir for the Treatment of Mild or Moderate COVID-19 in Adults: A Meta-Analysis. Cureus. 2023;15(5):e38586.
61. Palleti Sujith K. Subarachnoid Hemorrhage in Autoimmune Vasculitis: A Rare Presentation of Systemic Lupus Erythematosus-Antineutrophil Cytoplasmic Autoantibody-Associated Vasculitis Overlap Syndrome. Cureus. 2023;15(5):3.
62. Pranav S Garimella, Alan T Hirsch. Peripheral artery disease and chronic kidney disease: clinical synergy to improve outcomes. Adv Chronic Kidney Dis. 2014;21(6):460-71.

63. Zaid Munir , Muhammad Akash, Fnu Jaiprada, Bilal Abu Tarboush, Osama Ijaz, Anan Bseiso, et al. Evaluation of the Effects of Extracorporeal Shockwave Therapy in Patients with Peripheral Arterial Disease: A Meta-Analysis of Randomized Control Trials. Cureus. 2023;15(2):e34729.
64. Zha Yan, Qi Qian. Protein nutrition and malnutrition in CKD and ESRD. Nutrients. 2017;9(3):208.
65. Just Paul M. Reimbursement and economic factors influencing dialysis modality choice around the world. Nephrol Dial Transplant. 2008;23(7):2365-73.
66. Palleti Sujith Kumar, Melanie Padgett Powers. Practices Face Triple Whammy of Inflation, Payment Cuts, and Staff Shortages. 2023.
67. Fergus J Caskey, Sarah Wordsworth, Thomas Ben, Frank T de Charro, Catherine Delcroix, Vladimir Dobronravov, et al. Early referral and planned initiation of dialysis: what impact on quality of life?. Nephrol Dial Transplant. 2003;18(7):1330-8.
68. Lim, Mary Ann, Jatinder Kohli, and Roy D. Bloom. Immunosuppression for kidney transplantation: Where are we now and where are we going?. Transplant Rev (Orlando). 2017;31(1):10-17.
69. E F Vonesh, J J Snyder, R N Foley, A J Collins. Mortality studies comparing peritoneal dialysis and hemodialysis: what do they tell us?. Kidney Int Suppl . 2006;(103):S3-11.
70. Sujith K Palleti, Santhoshi R Bavi, Margaret Fitzpatrick, Anuradha Wadhwa. First case report of Sphingobium lactosutens as a human pathogen causing peritoneal dialysis-related peritonitis. Cureus. 2022;14(7):e27293.
71. Paul Komenda , Thomas W Ferguson , Kerry Macdonald, Claudio Rigatto, Chris Koolage, Manish M Sood, et al. Cost-effectiveness of primary screening for CKD: a systematic review. Am J Kidney Dis. 2014;63(5):789-97.
72. Grubbs V, Moss AH, Cohen LM, Fischer MJ, Germain MJ, Jassal SV, et al. A palliative approach to dialysis care: a patient-centered transition to the end of life. Clin J Am Soc Nephrol. 2014;9(12):2203-2209.
73. Himmelfarb J, Vanholder R, Mehrotra R, Tonelli M. The current and future landscape of dialysis. Nat Rev Nephrol. 2020;16(10):573-585.